

CASE STUDY: ANIMATION VEGETATION

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ABSTRACT

Animation Vegetation is a participatory design project to generate more green places in public spaces. As cities are growing everyday, due to the increasing number of people that are living in it, simultaneously accessibility to green spaces is decreasing. Which has a negative effect on the quality of life in build environments. The general idea of the project was to create something that engaged and enabled people to 'green-up' their local city area. The method deployed to trigger this kind of engagement was the design of an emotional tool. Inspired by bottom-up movements like graffiti artists and guerrilla gardeners, a doll out of a biodegradable textile was created. The doll grows in volume by filling it with seeds and soil. Steady watering and sunshine allow the seeds to hatch and find their way through the mazes of the textile. When fully grown, the idea is to drop the green doll into an urban setting that could use a bit more green. Different weather conditions cause the textile of the doll to degrade and become a part of the city. The doll acts as a graffiti tag on a city wall, making a critical statement about it's public surrounding.

Keywords: Participation, Design, Emotion, Urban, Green

INTRODUCTION

Animation vegetation started out in 2009 as a graduation project. As part of the graduation

exhibition, a tutorial – explaining how to make the doll from scratch - was developed and shared on the Animation Vegetation website (<http://www.animation-vegetation.be/>).

The tutorial and the website were created as an incentive for the Animation Vegetation project. To gain some insights in how people experience the process of nurturing the doll and placing it into an urban environment, an experiment was organised. Ten people were invited to adopt a doll, take care of it and - when transformed into a green doll - place it into an urban setting. Additionally, a diary was created that they could use to document their interactions with the doll.

This showed some very interesting results: people for example started coming up with names for their green character. Furthermore, the process of nurturing the doll was becoming a daily ritual for several participants.

Some people were even reluctant to put their doll into a public environment, since they were afraid it would be vandalised. This shows that the participants were becoming emotionally involved with their green character. The realisation that people could somehow emotionally connect with an environmental issue through an artefact was really important for the project. It provided in fact a starting point to engage people in contributing to the project.

CITY EXPERIMENT HEERLEN (NL)

After the first experiment, we were curious to see how the animation vegetation concept could work as a project. Immediately after the graduation exhibition, we got the opportunity to develop a pop-up lab for the project in the city of Heerlen, (NL). The context of the lab helped to engage people in the project. The space acted, as the project head quarters where participants could gather. Together with people from local art centre KUS (<http://www.kunstencentrumsigne.nl>), the gallery of the centre was transformed into a sewing workshop equipped with cutting tables, sewing machines, and filling materials.

People of the neighbourhood were invited to participate and make a doll for themselves. After taking the doll home, they started the process of nurturing it until the doll turned into a green character. At a pre-arranged moment, a guerrilla intervention in the centre of Heerlen was executed. This intervention resulted in about 50 dolls occupying the streets of Heerlen, making a collaborative statement about the importance of green in the public environment.

CITY EXPERIMENT HASSELT (BE)

In 2010, a new experiment in the city of Hasselt (BE) was setup. (<http://www.transplanthasselt.be/>). The objective was to enlarge the project and involve more people. This resulted in the creation of approximately 500 unfinished dolls in collaboration with some social working places.

We organised a call in the local newspaper and on the local broadcasting station, inviting the citizens of Hasselt to adopt one of the dolls.

Upon agreement, they received an empty doll that needed to be completed and nourished until it turned into a green character. When fully grown the participants had to pick a nice spot for the character within the city of Hasselt. The public reaction to the project was overwhelming; in a single day all of the dolls were adopted and 300 additional dolls were created so that people on the waiting list could join the project. From that moment on people started to make the dolls independently. Some participants started to experiment with different types of vegetation as stuffing for their character. Local elementary schools adopted several characters and used it in their educational programs. They used their dolls as a metaphor for taking care of nature.

REFLECTIONS

Reflecting on the design process of the project, it was really important that the project developed in several stages. From the first experiments to the city-scale project, each stage provided an import basis for the next one. During the gradation, animation vegetation was just a concept that started with a few bottom-up experiments. But gradually - as more organisations contributed -more people could be reached. Leaving things unfinished or open for the participants was also really important, since it created unexpected and interesting results. People started experimenting with different types of vegetation, started making clothes for the dolls or used it as an educational tool, it were the participants that made this design project work. When all participants placed their dolls into the city of Hasselt, the project became tangible for the local citizens. Not al interactions with the dolls were positive. Some of the dolls occupying the streets of Hasselt were vandalised and their internal seeds and soil were spilled on the pavement. The most important realisation of the project is that it did provoke as well positive and negative interactions.

